

EBFMC25-OP-84 · Evaluation of the Relationship Between Reflux and Oral and Dental Health in Pregnant Women

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: During pregnancy, physiological changes occur in both the oral cavity and the gastrointestinal system. Gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD) is a common condition during pregnancy and may negatively impact oral and dental health (Bai et al., 2013; Body & Christie, 2016). This study aims to evaluate the effects of GERD on oral health-related quality of life in pregnant women.

Materials and Methods: This single-center, cross-sectional study was conducted with 178 pregnant women in their second and third trimesters who presented to the Family Medicine Clinic of Gaziosmanpaşa Training and Research Hospital. Ethical approval was obtained from the Clinical Research Ethics Committee of the University of Health Sciences, Gaziosmanpaşa Training and Research Hospital (Decision No:325, Date: 08.09.2021). Face-to-face interviews were conducted to collect sociodemographic data. The Gastroesophageal Reflux Disease Questionnaire (GERD-Q) was used to assess reflux risk, the Oral Health Assessment Tool (OHAT) to evaluate oral health status, and the Oral Health Impact Profile-14 (OHIP-14) to measure oral health-related quality of life. Additionally, the Decayed, Missing, and Filled Teeth (DMFT) Index was determined. Data were analyzed using IBM SPSS Statistics 22, with statistical significance set at $p < 0.05$.

Results: The mean age of the participants was 27.62 ± 5.39 years, and the average gestational week was 31 ± 7.04 weeks. A significant association was found between the necessity for referral to a dentist and the presence of reflux risk ($X^2=4.251$, $p=0.050$). Based on OHAT scores, 69.03% ($n=78$) of the pregnant women requiring a dental referral had a low reflux risk (GERD-Q score < 8). Pregnant women at risk for reflux had significantly poorer oral health-related quality of life, as indicated by their OHIP-14 scores ($U=1648.0$, $p < 0.001$). A statistically significant positive correlation was observed between DMFT scores and OHAT scores ($r=0.428$, $p < 0.001$) as well as OHIP-14 scores ($r=0.413$, $p < 0.001$). Additionally, GERD-Q reflux risk scores were correlated with OHIP-14 scores ($r=0.222$, $p=0.003$). Pregnant women identified by OHAT as requiring a dental referral had approximately three times higher DMFT scores than those not requiring a referral (OR: 3.112 (1.875-5.165); $p < 0.001$).

Conclusion: This study demonstrated that gastroesophageal reflux negatively affects oral health-related quality of life in pregnant women and that more than half of the participants required referral to a dentist. The findings highlight the importance of emphasizing oral hygiene and dental health in pre-pregnancy counseling, as well as the necessity for timely interventions during pregnancy.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Oral health, pregnancy, gastroesophageal reflux

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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